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Annotation. Particular attention should be paid to the types of plants and flowers in the organization of the indoor landscape. Depending on the biological structure of the panel, it is necessary when the plants live in the interior. The article contains many solutions of many types of flowers that are useful for human health, how to take the file and how to transplant them.

Аннотация. Особое внимание уделено видам растений и цветов при организации ландшафтной структуры в помещении. В зависимости от биологической структуры панно необходимо, когда в интерьере живут растения. В статье дано множество решений о многих видах цветов, полезных для здоровья человека, о том, как взять пилку и как их пересадить.

Keywords: philodendron, purple, pelargonium, indoor flowering, transplant.

Ключевые слова: филодендрон, фиолетовый, пеларгония, комнатное цветение, пересадка.

Flowers and plants that grow indoors need special care. There are certain rules to follow when decorating a room with flowers. For example, some plants need a lot of light to flower normally, so you need to place them in a very bright place. In summer, many plants cannot live in the sun, but you can enjoy the sunshine in the morning and evening.

At the base we don't think about how much sunlight the plant will receive and where this room should be located. It looks really nice and can please us, but such a situation will only harm the plants. Plant disease is a very bad thing. Over time, this condition causes the wound to lengthen, bend, shrink, and eventually lose it. The lighting in each room is different. Even if the small room has a large window, only 40 percent of the street in front of the window, and as far as the corner of the room, here it is only 1 percent.

Based on this information, the best place to place indoor and decorative flowers and plants took the window. Located at a distance of no more than one meter, and in corners where it is not too dark, you can place aspidistra, philodendron, ficus, some grasses and the most shade-tolerant plants

If you have a lot of flowers collected in the window and this construction has a look, you can make it using thin boards to make it very soft, very effective. Better yet, or buy at a specialty store. In the steps of this staircase you can put pots of flowers. Those who love light should put it on the lower floors, and those who tolerate shade should put it on the upper rows. In some cases, we may not be able to put them in the office because they may not like too much light. They absorb a lot of light, weaken, and then die.

Purple, pelargoniums and balsam are sun-loving flowers. These and other plants are always exposed to sunlight, so they can sometimes have a very pleasing shape, one-sided rosettes and twisted stripes.

In order not to spoil this situation in your plants, you need to periodically rotate the pots so that they receive the same amount of light, evenly, without spoiling the appearance of the plant on each side of it. If you need to change your favorite plants in the room, it is permissible to place them in a place where there is less sunlight, for example, in the hallway, but this should not exceed two or three days. They are then returned to the window.

It's time to transplant every houseplant. After all, the amount of food they eat depends on the size of the pan. Each of the young plants should be replaced in the spring and in a few years, the old pots. For example, a palm tree under 3 years of age should be transplanted every 3-4 years, which is 5-7 years, and if it is more than 10 years - only after it has fallen asleep. Indoor flowers and plants need to be transplanted, as over time the available nutrients in the pot will decrease. In addition, its water permeability changes, the acidity of the soil increases, and the pot itself becomes smaller.

Most plants do not respond well to transplanting, so it is often not necessary to do so. Here's how to put one together for use with your indoor flower arrangement:

- you have noticed that the flowering of the plant is deteriorating, the flowers appear smaller and smaller than usual;

-The earth begins to crumble in the pot. This means that there are many roots in it;

-The roots begin to emerge from the bottom of the pot.

If you notice one or more of these, you should transplant immediately. As a rule, it is carried out in late winter or early spring. Approximately in February-March, that is, the plant is made from the rest period, sometimes - with the appearance of new leaves. If your plant is sick, you should definitely replant it without waiting for the right time.

Transplanted flowers should be stopped watering 3-4 days before transplanting, which is necessary to easily remove the soil from the pot. We take 2-3 inches from the top layer of earth and leave. Then we need to take another pan from the previous pan, which is 3-4 cm in diameter. Then, we need to cover the bottom holes of the new pan with a crack and fill it with a few inches of stone or you can use other drainage materials.

Then we need to prepare a ground mixture that is suitable for the plant. Now, with the right hand, we hit the bottom of the plant with a straw and shake it. We gently shake the roots off the ground using a wooden stick, when a large and rotten root is found, they should be cut off and sprinkled with charcoal dust on the sliced area. The previous pans are washed, rinsed with boiling water.

The roots of the newly transplanted plant should be carefully spread over the soil cone and filled with a little soil mixture. At the same time, shake a little to avoid gaps between the roots.

After the transplant process is done, we need to place the pot in a place where it is not exposed to direct sunlight. Such a plant should not be watered for another five days.

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